

SPECIALTY LANGUAGE AS A FACTOR OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PHARMACEUTICAL STUDENTS IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract: the article contains information about teaching English to students of non-linguistic specialties, pharmaceutical universities, the actual task of which is to master the knowledge of the terms of the specialty and obtain them, aimed at further use in the pharmaceutical field.

Аннотация: статья содержит информацию о преподавании английского языка студентам неязыковых специальностей фармацевтических вузов, актуальной задачей которых является овладение знаниями терминов специальности и их получение, направленное на дальнейшее использование в фармацевтической сфере.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada nolingvistik mutaxassisliklar, farmatsevtika oliy o'quv yurtlari talabalariga ingliz tilini o'rgatish to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar mavjud bo'lib, ularning dolzarb vazifasi mutaxassislik atamalari bo'yicha bilimlarni o'zlashtirish va ularni keyinchalik farmatsevtika sohasida qo'llashga qaratilgan.

Key words: learning, English, pharmacy students, skills, language learning

In modern conditions of expanding international economic relations, there is a need to train highly qualified specialists with such a level of knowledge of foreign languages that allows direct communication with foreign partners in professional activities.

In the context of teaching English to students of non-linguistic specialties of universities, an urgent task is to master their knowledge of the terms of the specialty and acquire the skills and abilities to use highly specialized vocabulary to perform educational professionally oriented tasks aimed at further communication.

Although knowledge of English is already a valuable skill in itself, without knowledge of pharmaceutical English terminology, pharmacists will not be able to understand words and expressions, because English for pharmacists is significantly different from traditional English. Knowledge of pharmaceutical English is a separate skill for a professional pharmacist.

In modern methodology, the problem of teaching professionally oriented vocabulary is covered quite widely. However, the issues of the formation of

professionally oriented lexical competence among pharmaceutical students have not been fully resolved. In this regard, the teaching environment is quite clearly aware of the need for further improvement of the methodology for the formation of professionally oriented lexical competence among students of the pharmaceutical specialty. The main problem is that pharmacy students are offered to master the basics of classification of pharmacological groups of drugs, their use, classification of diseases and symptoms in a short time, and understanding of special literature is impossible without background knowledge.

One of the main tasks facing teachers of foreign languages in a non-linguistic university is to teach pharmaceutical students to understand and translate professional texts from a foreign language into Russian. The higher school graduates the specialists of different profiles. Mastering their specialty and preparing for future professional activities, students master special vocabulary and terminology, skills and abilities to read special literature, speak and write on topics and problems of their chosen specialty.

Interest in a foreign language specialty has steadily increased since the 19th century. Today, the analysis of specialty languages is part of the disciplines of applied linguistics, where special attention is paid to terminological regulation in the translation of special texts and ensuring their understanding [3, p. 5].

The language of a specialty is a set of all linguistic means that are used in a limited specialty area of communication in order to ensure mutual understanding of people employed in this area. Other characteristics of the specialty language are also distinguished: primary connection with other specialties; oral and written use in special and interdisciplinary areas of communication; official application, choice and frequency of use of language means in vocabulary sections; tendency to standardize terminology and structure of texts. In the description of the structure of the specialty language, three planes interacting in the process of communication are distinguished: 1) lexical-terminological, 2) morphological-syntactic, and 3) textual [1, p. 45]. The teacher has to cooperate and enter into partnership and cooperation with students in order to successfully remove the difficulties of professional issues in the language of the specialty through joint efforts. The introduction of new information to already known blocks of professional information can also serve as a means of motivating learning, especially for students with high professional competence. The intensification of teaching professional foreign language

activities on the basis of the communicative method for teaching a foreign language of a specialty contributes to mobility in the study of the profession, as well as the success of the activity, which meets the requirements of professional training of specialists. Students gain a deeper understanding of the culture of the studied texts and instructions for pharmaceutical preparations in English.

The educational professional context of mastering the language of a specialty contributes to the understanding of the system and structure of the language, the correction of lingua communicative skills and abilities. The emphasis of training is shifted to the thematically-content plan of professionally oriented educational materials close to authentic

word usage in purposeful communication. At the same time, group communication dominates in educational social contacts [4, p. 274].

The texts for reading are accompanied by assignments for drawing up summary conclusions; describe, explain, compare, evaluate, summarize, etc. Taking into account the referential function of communication stimulates the implementation of the communicative impact on the partner of educational communication and on his speech actions.

The main goal of learning to abstract special texts should be the formation of the supralinguistic ability of discourse (i.e., the focus on teaching the message of the content of seen or heard professional information) and the technique of its language processing, as well as abstraction and contextualization in progression: from description, presentation, report, analysis - to the statement, judgment, argumentation, justification, discussion, acceptance of a point of view on textual materials, diagrams, diagrams, tables, etc. It is essential to develop students' autonomy of learning, especially when teaching reading authentic specialized literature and, first of all, the skills of operating with reference manuals. There is also a need for a specific linguistic and language-related range of skills related to the technique of receptive and productive processing of oral and written special texts into monological and dialogic forms [4, p. 276].

In the process of mastering the vocabulary of the studied language of the specialty, students themselves build career-oriented statements in which this vocabulary is used along with previously known material. Thus, the actual creative use of the newly learned vocabulary in communicative situations takes place, which ensures the formation of the skill of transferring information, which is very important for the development of oral speech. The new vocabulary of the specialty language acts as the basis for a thematically unified dialogic text, logically connects the dialogue and provides an increase in the volume of

linguistic material in accordance with the principle of inclusion. In the course of participation in the educational dialogue, students receive information about the terms in the studied language of the specialty. The need to reveal a word of meaning that is adequate to the concepts of terms forces students to be attentive to all textual material, since the incomprehensible meaning of at least one of these words will not allow them to participate in a dialogue in which the concepts denoted by new words are central and therefore often repeated.

The greatest difficulty for mastering is the general scientific vocabulary, located at the junction of the literary language and colloquial speech. Compared with special terms, which are relatively freely semantized in a situational context of dialogue that is understandable to a future specialist and, as a rule, does not present any particular difficulties for memorization, general scientific vocabulary and phraseology require constant attention. In order to intensively master the general scientific dictionary, in which there are much more polysyllabic words than in everyday colloquial, it is recommended to use transformational and substitution conditional communicative exercises, compose questions and answers to special texts and perform direct and reverse translation of text segments when updating vocabulary and phraseology general scientific layer of students' speech in a foreign language of the specialty. When compiling training conditional communicative exercises, teachers should pay special attention to words and phrases that are located on the border between service and autonomous words, i.e. unions, allied phraseological units, adverbs and prepositional phrases expressing various logical and syntactic connections - temporary (precedence, simultaneity, following the action), causal relationships, consequences, conditions, assumptions, goals, concessive meanings, etc.

It is necessary to emphasize the national-language basis of vocational training. There is no specialty language and scientific style at all; there is a professional communication in English, English scientific and technical style, etc. When teaching the language of a specialty and professional communication, the features of a scientific text and international elements of terminology are mastered as the literary norm of a particular language.

If the task of special departments is to teach the student the basic concepts of individual branches of science, then the task of a teacher of a foreign language is to help master the terminology of the specialty and written and oral professional speech.

There is an urgent need to train professionals capable of accurately translating pharmaceutical texts of various genres in written and oral form.

Without special textbooks and dictionaries, this task is difficult to accomplish, since currently pharmaceutical and medical translation manuals are offered to students of pharmacy, containing translation equivalents of individual terms and terminological phrases out of connection with integral terminological systems.

Professional communication implies not only fluency in a foreign language within the limits of possible social contacts, but also fluency in professionally oriented vocabulary, which a student masters in the process of reading literature in his specialty. The conditions for professionally oriented teaching of students of the Faculty of Pharmacy in a foreign language are reading authentic texts, the need to familiarize them with general, medical and pharmaceutical terminology, the formation of skills for independent work on creating an individual dictionary and mastering the skills of oral professional communication that proceeds as scenarios for the most common situations of everyday communication that are necessary and for professional communication.

In order to prepare a future pharmacist student to discuss the issues that make up the content of his professional training, it is necessary to select texts on pharmacology, pharmacognosy, botany, which allow the formation of pragmatic skills that would give the pharmacist student the opportunity to navigate in the literature in their specialty. Modern conditions for the development of society dictate a new model of teaching a foreign language, which makes it possible to quickly and efficiently teach students not only receptive skills, but also reproductive and productive ones.

The main principles on which the technology of intensive communicative teaching of a foreign language of a specialty should consistently be based are: humanization, intensification and activity activation, communication, professional orientation and professionalization of training and self-study, creative self-realization of the student's personality.

To conclude, the methodology of teaching a foreign language on the material of a scientific text, on the material of the language of the specialty, allows, first of all, with its orientation to rely on the text as the highest communicative unit of education.

References:

1. Bagrova A.Ya. Formation of communicative skills in reading / / Communicative orientation of teaching foreign. languages in non-language. university. – M.: MGLU, 1998. – S. 44–50.

2. Belyaeva A.S. Fundamentals of building classroom lessons in a foreign language in non-linguistic universities: Monograph. - Voronezh: Voronezh Publishing House, University, 1987. - 182 p.
3. Bim I.L., Sadomova L.V.: Some actual problems of organization of teaching foreign languages // Inostr. lang. at school. - 1998. - No. 6. - P. 4-10.
4. Borozenets G.K. Vocational teaching of a foreign language in a non-linguistic university based on the native language // Sat. scientific tr. Vseros. scientific method, conf. - Tolyatti: TolPI, VUiT, 1999. - S. 273-277.
5. Kalmykova E.I. Conditions for the formation of linguistic and communicative competence // Formation of communicative foreign language competence. - Issue. 437. - M.: MGLU, 1998. - S. 24-33.

